

A metagenomic study of antibiotic resistance genes in a hypereutrophic subtropical lake contaminated by anthropogenic sources

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HIGHLIGHTS

- First detailed ARGs analysis in a hyper-eutrophic subtropical lake.
- Lake Cajititlán harbors a reservoir of 475 antibiotic resistance genes.
- *Pseudomonas* and *Stenotrophomonas* are major reservoirs of ARGs.
- Multidrug resistance genes dominant in Lake Cajititlán bacteria.
- Strategies are needed to mitigate the spread of antibiotic resistance.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) are a major threat to human and environmental health. This study investigated the occurrence and distribution of ARGs in Lake Cajititlán, a hypereutrophic subtropical lake in Mexico contaminated by anthropogenic sources (urban wastewater and runoff from crop and livestock production). ARGs (a total of 475 genes) were detected in 22 bacterial genera, with *Pseudomonas* (144 genes), *Stenotrophomonas* (88 genes), *Mycobacterium* (54 genes), and *Rhodococcus* (27 genes) displaying the highest frequencies of ARGs. Among these, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* showed the highest number of ARGs. The results revealed a diverse array of ARGs, including resistance to macrolides (11.55 %), aminoglycosides (8.22 %), glycopeptides (6.22 %), tetracyclines (4 %), sulfonamides (4 %), carbapenems (1.11 %), phenicols (0.88 %), fluoroquinolones (0.44 %), and lincosamides (0.22 %). The most frequently observed ARGs were associated with multidrug resistance (63.33 %), with *MexF* (42 genes), *MexW* (36 genes), *smrD* (31 genes), *mtrA* (25 genes), and *KHM-1* (22 genes) being the most common. Lake Cajititlán is a recreational area for swimming, fishing, and boating, while also supporting irrigation for agriculture and potentially acting as a drinking water source for some communities. This raises concerns about the potential for exposure to antibiotic-resistant bacteria through these activities. The presence of ARGs in Lake Cajititlán poses a significant threat to both human and environmental health. Developing strategies to mitigate the risks of antibiotic resistance,

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including improving wastewater treatment, and promoting strategic antibiotic use and disposal, is crucial. This study represents a significant advancement in the understanding of antibiotic resistance dynamics in a hyper-eutrophic subtropical lake in a developing country, providing valuable insights for the scientific community and policymakers.

1. Introduction

Emerging contaminants (ECs) such as pharmaceuticals (including hormones and antibiotics), micropollutants, pesticides, and others, are ubiquitous environmental pollutants in aquatic systems. ECs are released through different pathways including urban wastewater and livestock runoff, and can be absorbed by organisms that inhabit the affected ecosystems, ultimately posing a risk to ecological and human health (Carter et al., 2019; Quincey et al., 2022). The presence of antibiotics in the environment is a pressing concern because of their potential for selection or maintenance of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs). These ARGs can be transferred between different bacteria and resistant bacteria can be transferred across humans, animals, and the environment, posing a serious threat to human health. In 2019, the number of deaths attributed to antibiotic resistance reached 1.27 million (95 % UI 0.911–1.71) (Murray et al., 2022), and it has been estimated that it will cause 10 million deaths annually by 2050 (Thompson, 2022).

Antibiotics are widely used in livestock production and humans for disease treatment. However, their excessive use and the lack of treatment in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) intended to eliminate these pollutants can cause water pollution (Van Boeckel et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2015; Henriksson et al., 2018; Klein et al., 2018). While limited, datasets of antibiotics in surface waters are available in the United States, many European countries, and China. However, there is a need for a substantially more comprehensive assessment of antibiotic contamination on a global scale, with a particular emphasis on Latin America (LA) and other developing countries (Li et al., 2013; Danner et al., 2019; Anh et al., 2021; Peña-Guzmán et al., 2019; Reichert et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2021; Souza et al., 2022; Maghsodian et al., 2022). Antibiotics are understudied in LA, where 81 % of the population lives in urban areas with limited access to clean water and sewage disposal (Valdez-Carrillo et al., 2020). Mexico, which is the second-largest economy in LA, is reported to be one of the top consumers of antibiotics in the region (SRE, 2023). In LA, over 50 % of the wastewater is released into the environment untreated (Rizzo et al., 2013; Souza et al., 2022). Unfortunately, wastewater treatment WWTPs in Mexico and many other countries lack proper regulations and technology to effectively remove many of the antibiotics, resulting in the discharge of antibiotics into water and sediments (Martínez-Orgániz et al., 2021). If the antibiotics persist in the environment at concentrations that are conducive to the selection of antibiotic-resistant bacteria (ARB), they may contribute to the emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance (WHO, 2018).

Lake Cajititlán (located in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga, Jalisco) is a small, shallow, subtropical, and endorheic lake (lacking outflow). It is the second most important natural water reservoir in Jalisco and is close to the metropolitan area of Guadalajara with a population of 5.3 million. Unfortunately, the lake is heavily contaminated due to the discharge of untreated or partially treated urban wastewater, and runoff from livestock production, which is the main economic activity in the lake's watershed. This nutrient pollution has precipitated eutrophication within Lake Cajititlán, fostering an environment conducive to the proliferation of algae and other aquatic plants, thereby reducing dissolved oxygen levels (de Anda et al., 2019; Gradilla-Hernández et al., 2020; Díaz-Torres et al., 2021). This ecological imbalance has led to recurrent fish kill events since 2013, closely associated with agricultural runoff that enhances phytoplankton blooms, thus depleting oxygen and blocking sunlight essential for aquatic life (de Anda et al., 2019). The potential contamination of the lake by ECs,

including antibiotics, poses an additional threat by potentially facilitating the emergence and propagation of ARGs within the lake's microbial communities. The contamination not only undermines the lake's ecological integrity but also threatens public health, given the local reliance on the lake for fishing, irrigation, and recreational activities. The presence of antibiotics could exacerbate fish mortality by promoting disease susceptibility, further affecting the lake's fishery resources and the health of the local community reliant on these resources (Pereiro et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2014). The significance of pollution extends beyond ecological impacts, influencing food security and public health due to potential antibiotic resistance transmission through the consumption of contaminated fish (Arsène et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2022). This underlines the urgent need for integrated strategies to mitigate pollution and its broad-ranging consequences.

Despite the growing body of research on the environmental impact of ECs and ARGs, significant gaps remain in our understanding, particularly concerning their dynamics in hypereutrophic subtropical lakes like Lake Cajititlán. This study aims to fill this critical gap by employing shotgun metagenomics, an approach that has yet to be extensively applied in the analysis of ARGs in hypereutrophic subtropical lakes. This methodology allows for an unprecedented insight into the identification, relative abundance, and distribution of ARGs, as well as the microbial communities harboring them (Ekwanzala et al., 2020; de Abreu et al., 2021). By mapping the presence and potential for dissemination of ARGs within Lake Cajititlán, this research seeks to elucidate the intricate web of interactions contributing to antibiotic resistance in aquatic ecosystems. This analysis is crucial for developing integrated pollution management strategies and understanding the broader implications for public health and ecological balance. Thus, our study not only fills a significant research void by detailing the ARG landscape in Lake Cajititlán but also sets a precedent for future investigations into antibiotic resistance in similar ecological settings.

The objective of this study was to use shotgun metagenomics to analyze ARGs in Lake Cajititlán, a hypereutrophic subtropical lake contaminated by anthropogenic sources. This research provides valuable insights into the extent of antibiotic resistance in the lake's microbial community and will help understand the potential risks posed to the environment and human health. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to focus on a better understanding of antibiotic resistance in a hypereutrophic subtropical lake.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area and sampling

Lake Cajititlán is a subtropical endorheic lake located approximately 25 km from Guadalajara, Mexico's second largest city (Caro-Becerra et al., 2017). The lake has an annual average surface area of 17.44 km², a maximum depth of 5.4 m, and an average storage volume of approximately 70.89 hm³. The altitude of the lake is 1551 m above sea level. It is classified as a warm polymictic lake and is situated in an endorheic basin surrounded by small hills with an area of approximately 201.8 km² (de Anda et al., 2019; Fig. 1). The basin experiences three seasons: the hot-dry season (February–May), wet season (June–September), and cold-dry season (October–January) (Gradilla-Hernández et al., 2020). July receives the highest rainfall (253 mm), followed by August (149 mm), and September (137 mm) (CONAGUA, 2021). The average maximum temperature in July, August, and September is 26 °C. The ecosystem-specific water quality index (ES-WQI) for Lake Cajititlán has the lowest values in

July according to historical annual trends (2009–2017; Díaz-Torres et al., 2021).

The largest town around the lakeshore is Cajititlán (8000 inhabitants). Other nearby towns include San Miguel Cuyutlán (7200 inhabitants), San Lucas Evangelista (2500 inhabitants), Cuexcomatitlán (2300 inhabitants) and San Juan Evangelista (2200 inhabitants). The main land use in the area surrounding the lake is agriculture, followed by human settlements and forests (IEEG, 2021; Fig. S1).

During the rainy season from July to September 2018, water samples were collected once a month at five sampling stations (CEA-01, CEA-02, CEA-03, CEA-04, and CEA-05; Fig. 1; Table S1) at three depths (80 cm, middle of the water column, and the top layer of the sediment) for metagenomic analysis and ARG screening. Water samples were collected using a Van Dorn water sampler and transferred into sterilized 1-liter plastic bottles. Two duplicates of each sample (2 L each) were collected, resulting in a total of 90 samples.

2.2. DNA extraction and metagenomic shotgun sequencing

Initially, each 2 L replicate of the water sample was filtered using a cellulose nitrate membrane (Whatman™) with a pore size of 20–25 µm. Subsequently, the resulting filtrate underwent a secondary filtration step through a cellulose nitrate membrane with a pore size of 0.45 µm (Whatman™). Once filtered, the membranes were stored frozen at –20 °C until the DNA extraction. DNA was extracted from both 20–25 µm and 0.45 µm membranes using the MP Biomedicals FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil, and the DNA concentration was measured using a NanoDrop ND-1000 UV–Vis spectrophotometer.

The DNA from each replicate was extracted and pooled by sampling depth at each site and month of sampling, resulting in 30 pooled samples (2 replicates per sample × 5 sampling sites × 3 months × 1 (pool of sampling depths) = 30). These samples were cleaned and quantified using the AMPure XP kit and Qubit 2.0 fluorometer, respectively, with purity analysis conducted by measuring the absorbance ratios at 260/280 and 260/230 nm NanoDrop ND-1000 UV–Vis spectrophotometer. The samples were sequenced using the Illumina Novaseq6000 platform, generating 2 × 150 bp paired-end reads and 5 Gb of clean data per sample. Sequencing was performed at the National Genomic Sequencing

Laboratory, Tec-BASE (Tecnologico de Monterrey).

2.3. Bioinformatic analysis of Lake Cajititlán Metagenomes

Raw reads were processed and analyzed using the OmicsBox 2.0.36 bioinformatics software (BioBam Bioinformatics, 2019). The pre-processing step involved the use of Trimmomatic, which removes contaminant sequences, adapters, short and low-quality reads, and trimmed bases (Bolger et al., 2014). The quality of the preprocessed reads was verified using the FASTQ tool (Andrews, 2010). The high-quality paired-end reads for each sample were subjected to metagenomic assembly using the metaSPAdes assembly toolkit, which employs several pipelines based on the de Bruijn graph (Nurk et al., 2017). Finally, we used Kraken2 v.2.1.2 software to annotate the resulting assemblies with the RefSeq v.2021.04 database and obtain the microbial composition of Lake Cajititlán (Wood and Salzberg, 2014; Wood et al., 2019).

2.4. Screening for antibiotic resistance genes in assembled metagenomes

ARGs were detected using the ABRicate software, which contains multiple databases (Zankari et al., 2012; Gupta et al., 2014; Jia et al., 2017; Feldgarden et al., 2019; Seemann, 2023). The ABRicate software compares all ARGs in the database with the genes in the input contigs to obtain sequence similarities. Genes that show similarity to ARGs in the database are predicted as potential ARGs; the higher the similarity, the more likely it is that the contig contains that resistance gene (Xihui et al., 2023). In this study, ARGs were identified from the assembled reads (metaSPAdes) by comparing the gene sequences with the NCBI, CARD, Resfinder, and ARG-ANNOT databases in ABRicate. Only results with query coverage of >90 % and sequence identity of >70 % were retained. Furthermore, for statistical analysis and graphical representation of the results, focus was placed on the results obtained from the CARD database. This database provided the highest number of ARGs, and hits had higher coverage and similarity compared to hits to other databases.

Fig. 1. Locations of the sampling points in Lake Cajititlán. SM: San Miguel Cuyutlán WWTP; CAJ: Cajititlán WWTP; SJE: San Juan Evangelista WWTP. Sampling points: CEA-01 to CEA-05.

2.5. Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were conducted using RStudio software (R version 4.3.0; R Core Team, 2023) and Python using the Jupyter Notebook software (version 6.5.2; Kluyver et al., 2016). Bar graphs of relative read abundance (>0.01 %) across the sampling months were plotted with ggplot2 and scale libraries in R (Wickham, 2016; Wickham and Seidel, 2022).

An extensive literature search was conducted to compile commonly detected antibiotic-resistant bacterial species (ARBS) in hospital, agricultural, and livestock farming environments in Mexico (Miranda et al., 2009; Amabile-Cuevas, 2010; Garza-González et al., 2010, 2020; Zaidi et al., 2012, 2015; Martínez-Vázquez et al., 2018; Maradiaga et al., 2019; Torumkuncy et al., 2022). This search was performed using PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus databases. Subsequently, the compiled species were used to filter the taxonomic data obtained in this study, then reads normalization was performed using DESeq2 package (Love et al., 2014) and represented using a bar graph showing the total normalized sequence reads associated with each species per sampling month (library: ggplot2; Wickham, 2016).

To analyze the frequency of observed ARGs detected in the contigs of the shotgun metagenomic data of this study, a bar graph was generated using the ggplot2 library (Wickham, 2016). Given that the CARD database yielded the highest number of ARGs, as well as greater coverage and similarity of the hits compared to other databases, a more detailed analysis of these results was conducted. First, a chord diagram was employed to visualize the associations and distribution between resistance to different classes of antibiotics by sampling site and month, using the circular package in R (Gu et al., 2014). Additionally, principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) was performed to explore possible differences in ARG distribution between different sampling sites and months. First, the ARG counts were normalized using the DESeq2 package (Love et al., 2014). Subsequently, the vegan package (Oksanen et al., 2022) and vegdist() function of R were used to calculate distances based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities. Then, these distances were used in cmdscale to perform a Multidimensional Classical Scaling Analysis (MDS), obtaining coordinates in a reduced-dimensional space. To test for significant differences in ARG distribution, a permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) and analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) were performed. These tests allowed for the evaluation of the temporal and spatial differences in the distribution of ARGs. The vegan package and the adonis2() and anosim() functions of base R were used for these analyses (Clarke, 1993; Anderson, 2001; Anderson et al., 2006; Warton et al., 2012).

To visualize the relationships and patterns among the complete set of ARGs detected in a specific bacterial genus and their association with the corresponding antibiotic class, a heatmap graphical representation was generated. To perform this visualization, the R programming environment was employed, along with the igraph library (Csardi and Nepusz, 2006). For a more detailed analysis of ARGs in terms of their frequency of occurrence in the samples and their association with other genes and their products (antibiotic classes), a co-occurrence network analysis was conducted using Python and the NetworkX library (Hagberg et al., 2008). Finally, the results obtained from ABRicate for ARBS were presented using a bar graph in R, employing the ggplot2 library (Wickham, 2016). Only the species with the highest frequencies of occurrence of ARGs in the samples were highlighted in this graph, providing a clear visualization of the most relevant species in the context of the study.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Bioinformatic analysis and comparison of bacterial community composition

Sequencing of all the samples yielded 748,721,392 raw reads and 59,236,568 contigs (Table S2). Kraken2 was used to annotate the reads

with the RefSeq v.2021_04 reference database, resulting in 29,544,581 reads (49.87 %) classified within the bacterial taxonomic domain (46.45 %) (Table S2). The diversity and abundance of the bacterial communities at the genus level were assessed during different sampling months using read relative abundance bar plots (Fig. 2). In this study, *Pseudomonas* (24.22 %), *Streptomyces* (13.76 %), *Flavobacterium* (8.98 %), and *Acidovorax* (8.44 %) bacterial genera were consistently the most abundant across all sampling months (Table S3). These findings coincide with those of other studies in aquatic environments with different trophic states that used a metagenomic approach and obtained some of these genera as the most dominant, except for the genus *Acidovorax* (Song et al., 2022; Mao et al., 2023). However, some studies have isolated strains of the *Acidovorax* genus from surface and groundwater contaminated with organic and inorganic compounds (Monferrán et al., 2005; Ghosh and Sar, 2013; Yavari-Bafghi et al., 2023). These contaminants include herbicides, pesticides, hydrocarbons, and heavy metals. *Acidovorax* bacteria can degrade these contaminants using a variety of metabolic pathways, including enzymes that break down the contaminant molecules or detoxify the contaminants (Singleton et al., 2009; Mulet et al., 2011). In the Lake Cajititlán basin, where agriculture is the primary economic activity, the presence of herbicides and pesticides is likely pronounced (Díaz-Torres et al., 2022a, 2022b). This environmental context could potentially favor the proliferation of *Acidovorax* in the lake, where it may serve as a bioremediation agent. However, further research is needed to elucidate the specific mechanisms by which *Acidovorax* may mitigate agricultural pollutants in the lake.

A study conducted in five urban lakes with different trophic states in China found that *Streptomyces*, *Polynucleobacter*, and *Pseudomonas* were the most dominant genera across all trophic states (Mao et al., 2023). Conversely, *Flavobacterium* has been frequently observed with high abundance in eutrophic and hypertrophic water bodies, which is in agreement with the trophic conditions of Lake Cajititlán (Drury et al., 2013). Some specific bacterial genera were absent during certain months (abundance, <0.01 %). For example, *Acinetobacter* was observed only in July, *Agrobacterium* in September, *Nocardioideis* in July and August, and *Rhizobium* in August and September. These results indicate that the abundance of these bacteria fluctuates temporally in Lake Cajititlán. One possibility is that environmental conditions (temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, etc.) influence bacterial growth (Díaz-Torres et al., 2021). Additionally, seasonal factors, such as temperature fluctuations, nutrient influx from rainfall runoff, predation by protists and ciliates, infection by specific phages, competition for resources between bacterial genera, variations in sedimentation rates, wind-driven mixing events, and anthropogenic activities like wastewater discharge and agricultural runoff, might contribute to these variation (Meng et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019; Díaz-Torres et al., 2021, 2022a; Yang et al., 2019).

Based on a comprehensive literature search and the taxonomic and ARGs annotation results obtained in this study, our findings suggest that certain ARBS found in Lake Cajititlán may come from hospital, crop plants and livestock sources. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* was the most abundant species that may have come from agricultural sources, followed by *Pseudomonas syringae*, the latter was more abundant in September (Fig. 3A). According to the literature, these changes suggest several influencing factors, starting with seasonal changes that affect how plants and microorganisms interact (Chaloner et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2023). Furthermore, these patterns highlight a link between anthropogenic activity, water quality, and bacterial prevalence in crops, which ultimately affects the adjacent lakes (Burdon and Zhan, 2020; Domínguez et al., 2021). ARB in crops can have a significant indirect impact on public health, environmental integrity, and food supply chains (Founou et al., 2016). One potential pathway for the transmission of ARB from crops to humans is through the irrigation of vegetable plots with contaminated water. This is because any vegetable intended to be consumed raw may act as a vehicle for the spread of ARB and ARGs to humans, leading to higher rates of illness and more complex medical

Fig. 2. Relative read abundance bar plot of bacterial genera by sampling month, excluding other genera <0.01 % abundance, which account for ~60 % of the total reads (all depths and sites aggregated).

situations (Manyi-Loh et al., 2018a, 2018b). Additionally, the release of these resistant bacteria into the environment, originating from agricultural waste and polluted water, disrupts natural ecosystems and alters the balance of microbial ecology (including the displacement of native bacteria, the spread of disease, and the evolution of new ARGs; Lundborg and Tamhankar, 2017). All these factors underscore the need for responsible agricultural practices, proper antibiotic use, and robust surveillance to mitigate risks.

For the bacteria commonly found in the hospital sector, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was found to have the highest abundance in our study, followed by *Serratia marcescens* (Fig. 3B). *P. aeruginosa* is an opportunistic bacterial pathogen that adapts to thrive in a wide range of ecological niches and possesses the capability to infect individuals with compromised immune systems (Valot et al., 2015). *S. marcescens* can cause infections, particularly in immunocompromised patients and in those with open wounds (Moodley et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2021; Genera et al., 2022). Moreover, the presence of these bacteria and their associated ARGs is expected because antibiotics are not entirely metabolized by humans and therefore are excreted (Jelic et al., 2015), ultimately reaching the environment by sewage pipes. This facilitates the emergence and expansion of human antibiotic resistant pathogens with potential negative outcomes to public health.

In this study, the presence of both *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella enterica*, two bacteria commonly associated with the livestock farming sector, was identified. Both bacteria had a similar level of abundance over the three-month study period, with a higher abundance in September than in the previous months (Fig. 3C). It is important to note that within the broad category of *E. coli*, only specific strains pose significant concerns in veterinary and public health settings (Course et al., 2021). Notably, *E. coli* is widely distributed in the environment and is often employed as a bioindicator for monitoring antimicrobial resistance (AMR) dynamics (DeFrancesco et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2006). The antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of *E. coli* reflect the selective pressure exerted by antimicrobial usage, and these bacteria have the potential to serve as reservoirs of ARGs (European Food Safety Authority, 2012). These resistance genes, which are frequently found in their plasmids, can be shared among bacteria, including *Salmonella* spp., in

both humans and animals (Fluckey et al., 2007). *S. enterica* is a significant foodborne pathogen responsible for millions of human infections worldwide (Milho et al., 2019). Salmonellosis has clinical and economic implications for both beef and dairy cattle operations, leading to disease and financial losses (Genovese et al., 2004). The Agricultural and Fisheries Information Service of the Mexican government (SIAP, 2023) reports that Jalisco ranks second in beef production, with 200,000 tons of carcass meat produced annually. This amount represents the mobilization and slaughter of 280,000 cattle. Understanding the dynamics of bacterial prevalence in livestock may contribute to improved health management practices (Pradhan et al., 2009). However, it is important to note that we were unable to obtain specific information on the diseases prevalent in livestock populations in Jalisco. Additionally, considering the economic and tourist activities surrounding the lake, it is important to acknowledge that the current regulations regarding the presence of *E. coli* and *Salmonella* in animal feed products do not extend to water exposure (Secretaría de Salud, 1994, 2014). Efforts should be made to assess and mitigate the potential risks associated with transmission of these bacteria through water sources, particularly in areas where economic and tourism activities are prevalent.

Reports of infectious diseases in the population of Jalisco from 2018 to 2022 are documented in the Ministry of Health's Epidemiological Bulletin (Table S7), containing records of intrahospital clinical cases, clinical case reports, surveillance systems, and other epidemiological studies (SSA, 2023). Although cases treated outside affiliated health centers are missing, the bulletin provides the most comprehensive available record. *E. coli* is partially responsible for intestinal infections caused by non-specified organisms, whereas the *Salmonella* genus is responsible for four reported types of infections (typhoid fever, paratyphoid fever, other salmonellosis, and intestinal infections by other organisms and those that are poorly defined). These findings suggest that the prevalence and abundance of these bacteria associated with infectious diseases in the hospital, agriculture and livestock farming sectors around Lake Cajititlán may be an overlooked source of contamination to the lake.

Further research and surveillance are necessary to investigate the potential links between Lake Cajititlán, prevalence of infectious

Fig. 3. Antibiotic-resistant bacterial species with greater prevalence in the sectors of Mexico: agriculture (A), hospital (B), and livestock farming (C) – Normalized reads. Relative abundance data unnormalized reads in Supplementary Table 7.

diseases, and their impact on both human and environmental health. Understanding these relationships is crucial for implementing targeted interventions and preventive measures to mitigate the risk of contamination.

3.2. Analysis of ARGs frequencies and associations with antibiotic classes

ARGs were identified from the contigs by comparing gene sequences with multiple databases, including NCBI, CARD, Resfinder, and ARG-ANNOT using the ABRicate tool (Fig. 4). Among these databases, CARD yielded the highest number of ARGs (475 ARGs), and hits had higher coverage and similarity compared to hits to other databases (45.32 %; Table S4). For more detailed information, CARD results were selected among the other databases because CARD offers continuous curation of data every one to three months, a process that involves the review and mining of the latest scientific literature with human expert curation of data (Lal Gupta et al., 2020). Moreover, CARD provides a high number of ARG detections for shotgun metagenomic datasets in comparison with other databases, and is also useful for detecting multidrug-resistance genes (Alcock et al., 2023). Interestingly, our analysis revealed that the majority of the genes identified in CARD were multidrug-resistance genes, which may be caused by the extensive use of antibiotics in human therapies, livestock farming, and agriculture, as suggested by Catalano et al. (2022). The rise of multidrug-resistant bacterial pathogens that have acquired resistance genes against antibiotics in three or more classes has compromised the effectiveness of

traditional antibiotics, limiting treatment alternatives for diseases once easily manageable with these drugs (Imran et al., 2019; Terreni et al., 2021). This implies that new strategies must be developed to prevent the spread of the bacteria that contain multi-drug resistance genes (Terreni et al., 2021).

The NCBI database was the second most productive database in terms of ARG identification, followed by ARG-ANNOT, and Resfinder (Fig. 4, Table S4). Notably, each database yielded distinct results. Specifically, the NCBI database classified ARGs into 12 antibiotic classes, whereas CARD identified 10 classes. Resfinder identified ARGs associated with eight antibiotic classes, and ARG-ANNOT provided results for seven antibiotic classes (Table S4). Each database produced distinct results: while NCBI managed to identify most antibiotic classes, it was noticeably limited in its identification of multidrug-resistant classes. The ARG-ANNOT database failed to identify any multidrug-resistant class, possibly because of its primary design for bacterial genomes rather than environmental samples (Yang et al., 2016). As noted by Lal Gupta et al. (2020), Resfinder yielded lower counts of ARGs in comparison to other databases in the shotgun genome datasets. This observation underscores the absence of a single, definitive database for ARG identification. Consequently, employing multiple databases is crucial for gaining a comprehensive understanding of antibiotic resistance gene (ARG) diversity.

Two chord diagrams were constructed to visualize the associations and distribution of different classes of resistance genes based on the sampling site and month using the CARD database. The first diagram

Fig. 4. Frequency of ARGs encoding resistance to various antibiotics classes across multiple databases (NCBI, CARD, Resfinder, and ARG-ANNOT).

(Fig. 5A) depicts the associations between antibiotic classes across different sampling months, revealing a higher frequency of genes encoding resistance to various antibiotic classes in September. This could be due to several factors, such as seasonal changes in runoff, use of antibiotics by the population for medical purposes or for livestock (Pollard and Morra, 2017; Manyi-Loh et al., 2018b). In the lake basin, historical monthly precipitation trends reveal that July experiences the highest rainfall, followed by August, and then September (CONAGUA, 2021). There are multiple factors at play that make identifying causes difficult. More rain can cause water to flow over the ground, carrying pollutants. Nutrients from runoff can promote the growth of bacteria carrying ARGs. Additionally, these results may be the cumulative effect of the previous months of heavy rainfall. On the other hand, any nutrients entering the lake with runoff can stimulate growth in the lake, especially of copiotrophic bacteria, which are more likely to carry ARGs (Mukherjee and Chakraborty, 2006). The overall result of these changes or others could have resulted in a higher frequency of ARGs in September. This is consistent with a study published by Larsson and Flach (2022) which found that ARBs were more prevalent in water bodies contaminated with agricultural runoff.

The second diagram (Fig. 5B) illustrates the distribution of antibiotic classes across sampling sites, demonstrating that genes were generally associated in similar proportions across most sampling sites (CEA1–CEA4) within the lake, except for CEA5, where the frequency of genes observed was lower, and no multidrug genes were observed at this site. This could be attributed to several factors, including the potential influence of lake water flow (Pascual-Benito et al., 2020). The San Juan Evangelista (SJE) WWTP, which is nearest to CEA5 but not close, has the lowest discharge (5 L/s) among the three facilities serving Lake Cajititlán (Tlajomulco.gob.mx, 2014) and is thus not likely to have a large effect on CEA5 (Fig. 1). If lake water moves slowly around the

shallow lake, the time it takes for wastewater to reach CEA5 could be considerable, potentially allowing for substantial alteration of the bacterial community in route (Wang et al., 2021). However, further investigations are necessary to elucidate the specific mechanisms and factors influencing gene abundance variation across sampling sites, particularly regarding the impact of wastewater treatment processes and antibiotic input from healthcare facilities in the area.

The spatial and temporal variations in ARGs associated with the different classes of antibiotics displayed in the chord diagrams were further evaluated using PCoA, ANOSIM, and perMANOVA analysis (Fig. 5C and D). The results revealed no significant temporal or spatial differences in ARG classes (Table S6). The perMANOVA analysis for the sampling month yielded a non-significant result ($p = 1.000$), indicating that there were no temporal variations in the ARG classes. Similarly, the ANOSIM analysis for the sampling month showed a low R-value (-0.030) and a non-significant p-value ($p = 0.705$), further supporting the absence of temporal differences. These findings suggest that potential changes in specific genes may be obscured by opposing shifts in others. This complexity may contribute to an absence of statistically significant overall differences when considering all ARGs together. Regarding spatial variations, perMANOVA for sampling points indicated a lack of significant spatial differences in ARG classes ($p = 0.455$). The ANOSIM analysis for the sampling points also exhibited a low R-value (-0.055) and a non-significant p-value ($p = 0.833$), confirming the absence of spatial variations (Fig. 5C and D; Table S6). Previous studies conducted in Lake Cajititlán demonstrated no significant spatial differences in the composition of bacterial communities, functional profiles associated with biogeochemical cycles, or physicochemical parameters analyzed within this water body. However, significant temporal differences in these aspects have been reported (Díaz-Torres et al., 2021; Díaz-Torres et al., 2022a; Díaz-Torres et al., 2022b). The present study

Fig. 5. Analysis of ARG distribution through chord diagrams by sampling month (A), by sampling site (B), and PCoA comparative analysis by month (C) and sampling points (D). Sampling points: CEA1 to CEA5.

revealed no significant temporal or spatial variation in the distribution of ARG classes (Fig. 5C and D). This observation can be attributed to several factors. Lake Cajititlán’s location adjacent to urban areas is a likely contributor to the consistent presence of ARGs, as these areas often have higher rates of antibiotic use and discharge of wastewater containing antibiotic residues (Almaki et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2019; Junaid et al., 2022). If ARG frequencies are driven by sewage input into

the lake, which is likely relatively constant over the year, it would explain the lack of temporal variation. Additionally, the lake’s shallow depth, with an average of approximately two meters, facilitates thorough water mixing throughout the lake (Gradilla-Hernández et al., 2019). This mixing homogenizes the distribution of ARGs across the lake, resulting in the observed lack of spatial variation. Previous studies have also demonstrated the uniform distribution of microbial

communities and environmental conditions across Lake Cajititlán, attributing it to the lake’s polymictic nature (Díaz-Torres et al., 2021, 2022a). Such shallow subtropical lakes often experience total water column mixing throughout the summer, driven by precipitation and wind (Cavicchioli et al., 2019; Gradilla-Hernández et al., 2020).

Current evidence suggests that hospital wastewater is a significant contributor to antibiotic resistance in aquatic environments, particularly in multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacteria, as demonstrated by Hassoun-Kheir et al. (2020). In the case of Lake Cajititlán, its proximity to four healthcare facilities raises concerns, as the effluents from these

facilities are treated in the three WWTPs located on the shores of this lake (Fig. 1). Unfortunately, there are no proper regulations for removal of these compounds by WWTPs (Martínez-Orgániz et al., 2021).

3.3. Analysis of bacterial genera linked to antibiotic gene classes

The investigation of ARGs in aquatic environments is an emerging field (Kittinger et al., 2016; Ramos et al., 2020). Consequently, one objective of the present study was to explore the bacterial genera linked to resistance against a specific class of antibiotics, using samples

Fig. 6. Heatmap analysis of associations between bacterial genera and antibiotic resistance genes classes.

collected from Lake Cajititlán. To understand these relationships and patterns, a heatmap was generated, illustrating the associations among all identified genes within a particular bacterial genus and their corresponding antibiotic classes (Fig. 6).

ARGs (a total of 475 genes) were detected in 22 bacterial genera, with *Pseudomonas* (144 genes), *Stenotrophomonas* (88 genes), *Mycobacterium* (54 genes), and *Rhodococcus* (27 genes) displaying the highest prevalence of ARGs (Table S5). These genera are common in water (Vaz-Moreira et al., 2014). Furthermore, some of these genera share the same ARGs (*Pseudomonas* and *Stenotrophomonas*) (Table S5). Notably, *Pseudomonas* exhibited the highest number of distinct ARGs, with 14 ARGs identified (Fig. 6). Within this genus, three genes (*APH(6)-Id*, *APH(3')-VI*, and *APH(3')-Ib*) coded for resistance to aminoglycosides, whereas 11 genes were associated with multidrug resistance (*PER-1*, *MexWQKIFEB*, *CpxR*, and *AIM-1*). *Pseudomonas* sp. are opportunistic pathogens, commonly reported in water samples, that develop resistance to antibiotics through different mechanisms, such as horizontal gene transfer of resistance genes that produce a multidrug-resistant phenotype (Ahmed, 2022; Zhao and Hu, 2010). From these results, it can be inferred that *Pseudomonas* have more and multiple resistances to antibiotics. Moreover, according to certain studies that used whole genome sequencing to detect ARGs, this genus is more resistant to different classes of antibiotics, leading to the acquisition of ARGs, and the species *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is one of the most concerning hazards to public health (Ahmed, 2022).

Stenotrophomonas harbored nine ARGs where one gene (*sulI*) conferred resistance to sulfonamides, two genes (*ACC(6')-Iz* and *Iak*) were associated with aminoglycoside resistance, and the remaining six genes (*smerRFEDA* and *MexW*) were associated with multidrug resistance (Fig. 6). *Stenotrophomonas* is frequently found in aquatic environments, particularly in water bodies, such as rivers, wells, and lakes (Brooke, 2012; Looney, 2005; Looney et al., 2009). It has also been identified in animals, particularly aquatic species, and some of these animal associated strains seem to be genetically related to strains causing infections in humans, suggesting a possible strain or gene exchange (Abbott et al., 2011; Jayol et al., 2018). *S. maltophilia* is one of the less-known drug-resistant bacteria that can lead to challenging infections, and the presence of ARGs in this species raises concerns (Said et al., 2023). It is increasingly being isolated as a “newly emerging pathogen of concern”. The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes it as one of the most underestimated and significant multidrug-resistant organisms in hospitals because it can cause opportunistic infections with high morbidity and mortality rates, particularly in immunocompromised patients (Brooke, 2012; Said et al., 2023).

3.4. Comprehensive analysis of ARG and bacterial genus co-occurrence, and key species in resistant communities

To comprehensively understand ARG frequencies and their interconnections, we conducted a co-occurrence network analysis (Fig. S2). Our findings reveal *MexF* as the most prevalent ARG across samples, exclusively found in *Pseudomonas*. *MexF*, a member of the resistance-nodulation-division (RND) transporter family, plays a pivotal role in antibiotic resistance in various bacteria, including *P. aeruginosa* and *Burkholderia cenocepacia*. It is implicated in multidrug resistance by facilitating antibiotic and toxin efflux from bacterial cells (Guglielame et al., 2006; Lorusso et al., 2022). Consistent with our study, *Pseudomonas* harbors the highest number of distinct ARGs (Fig. 5), underscoring *MexF*'s significance as a prime target for further research and intervention strategies.

The next most prevalent ARGs in the samples were *KHM-1* and *MexW*, both of which encode resistance to multiple drugs. *KHM-1* is a metallo- β -lactamase that was first reported in the *Citrobacter freundii* strain KHM243 isolated in 1997 from a patient with a catheter-associated urinary tract infection in Japan (Sekiguchi et al., 2008). This strain is resistant to most β -lactams other than monobactams

(Umeda et al., 2020). In this study, the *KHM-1* gene was observed in *Citrobacter*, highlighting its presence in a clinically relevant context (Fig. 6.) Furthermore, the *MexW* gene, which is a part of the RND-type efflux complex *MexVW-OprM*, has been associated with AMR mechanisms in various pathogens. To date, no studies have reported the presence of this gene, except for the information available in the CARD database (Alcock et al., 2023). Moreover, the association between *KHM-1* and *MexW* has not been previously reported. The potential co-occurrence of *KHM-1* and *MexW* suggests a novel AMR mechanism, necessitating further study, such as metagenome-assembled genome analysis, to confirm their linkage and co-existence (Imran et al., 2019; Pal et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2022).

ARGs with singular connections, like *cphA5* (carbapenems), *mel* (multidrug), and *FOX-4* (multidrug) were identified, alongside others like *OXA-427*, *cfrC*, *CPS1*, *THIN-B*, and *vanRO* (the latter being notably prevalent) showing no connections (Fig. S1). ARGs such as *OXA-427* and *FOX-4*, offering resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, suggest broad roles in antibiotic resistance by binding to various antibiotics, exemplified by *OXA-427*'s ability against a range of beta-lactams (Nikaido, 2009; Bogaerts et al., 2017). Despite network analysis revealing ARG interactions, its ability to accurately identify specific relationships between resistance genes has limits, underscoring the importance of experimental validation for accurate resistance profiling (Aminov, 2009).

The *vanRO* gene was one of the most frequently observed genes, yet it also did not exhibit any connections (Fig. S2). Some ARGs independently confer resistance to specific antibiotics, suggesting that an organism only needs to contain one gene to be resistant to a particular antibiotic. However, it has been reported that bacteria harboring multiple resistance genes exhibit a higher level of resistance than those harboring a single gene (Jahantigh et al., 2020). A study of soil from the Tibetan Plateau of Mount Nyenchen Tanglha reported *vanRO* as one of the most abundant ARGs (Li et al., 2020). This gene confers resistance to glycopeptides and has primarily been isolated from *Rhodococcus equi*, consistent with the findings of our study, where *vanRO* was exclusively present in the *Rhodococcus* genus (Gudeta et al., 2014; Fig. 6). These findings not only underscore the significance of *vanRO* in antibiotic resistance but also present intriguing opportunities for further investigations into its mechanism of resistance and prevalence in aquatic systems.

Bar graphs were generated to highlight the genera with the highest number of ARGs in the samples (Fig. 7), based on the results presented in the heatmap (Fig. 6). *P. aeruginosa* emerged as the species with the greatest number of gene observations (>30) and highest diversity, with 14 distinct genes detected. Among these, three genes (*APH(6)-Id*, *APH(3')-VI*, and *APH(3')-Ib*) conferred resistance to aminoglycosides, whereas 11 genes were associated with multidrug resistance (*PER-1*, *MexWQKIFEB*, *CpxR*, and *AIM-1*). In metropolitan water bodies with characteristics like those of Lake Cajititlán, such as Lake Alalay in Bolivia, *P. aeruginosa* has been previously reported to contain multiple multidrug resistance genes like *MexF*, *MexQ*, *MexI*, *MexW*, *MexB*, *MexD*, and *MexK* (Quillaguamán et al., 2021), which were also found here. Miranda-Novales et al. (2020) tested blood and urine cultures from patients to establish the current situation of AMR and antibiotic usage in Mexican hospitals from 2016 to 2017. Their study revealed significant variability in *P. aeruginosa* species, displaying a broad range of AMR percentages across different hospitals. Therefore, considering the findings of this study, it can be inferred that this species poses a major threat to patients in hospitals.

Stenotrophomonas maltophilia ranked second in terms of ARG observations (>30) with nine different genes (Fig. 7). Among these, one gene (*sulI*) provided resistance to sulfonamides, two genes (*ACC(6')-Iz* and *Iak*) were associated with aminoglycoside resistance, and the remaining six genes (*smerRFEDA* and *MexW*) were associated with multidrug resistance. While the presence of these resistance genes does not directly increase the risk of infection by *S. maltophilia*, it does significantly

Fig. 7. ARG analysis of the most frequent antibiotic-resistant bacterial species.

elevate the risk of treatment failure and mortality among infected individuals. This is particularly concerning in immunocompromised patients, who are more susceptible to infections and less likely to respond effectively to antibiotic treatment (Chen et al., 2023). Given the widespread use of sulfonamides, aminoglycosides, and multiple drugs in healthcare settings, the presence of ARGs for these antibiotics in *S. maltophilia* poses a significant threat to human health.

Citrobacter freundii exhibited only two distinct ARGs (MOX-9 and KHM-1), both of which encoded multidrug resistance (Fig. 7). This opportunistic pathogen, which belongs to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, is commonly found in the human gut and feces of healthy individuals. Exposure to *C. freundii* has been linked to urinary and bloodstream infections, sepsis, and pneumonia in newborns (Owoseni and Okoh, 2017). Studies performed in Hidalgo, Mexico (Martínez-Hernández et al., 2013) and Eastern Cape Province, South Africa (Owoseni and Okoh, 2017), reported that *C. freundii* was tolerant to chlorination-based disinfection and was detected in chlorinated treated effluents. The abundance of *C. freundii* in the present study could be linked to its previously mentioned chlorine tolerance, indicating the need for further sanitation infrastructure and upgrade of currently available treatment processes.

Single types of ARGs have been observed in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (mtrA, conferring multidrug resistance), *R. equi* (vanRO, associated with glycopeptide resistance), and *Mycobacterium smegmatis* (RbpA, providing macrolide resistance; Fig. 7). The organic matter and nutrient load of receiving water bodies play an important role in *Mycobacterium*

spp. survival (Vaerewijck et al., 2005). Although the growth rate of *Mycobacterium* cannot typically overcome the dilution when an effluent enters a receiving water body, biofilm formation in water distribution systems can function as a reservoir for bacterial populations as biofilms are not removed with the flowing water (Xiang et al., 2014). The endorheic, and shallow nature of Lake Cajititlán (Gradilla-Hernández et al., 2019) can favor the formation of biofilms on suspended particulate matter, promoting the growth of *Mycobacterium*, as has been reported for other urban shallow water bodies (Esteban and García-Coca, 2018). *M. tuberculosis*, which carries the multidrug resistance gene mtrA, has also been identified in Lake Alalay, Bolivia (Quillaguamán et al., 2021), in accordance with our results.

R. equi, an emerging pathogen, causes lung infections such as pneumonia and abscesses in immunocompromised mammals. Its introduction into Lake Cajititlán may result from disposal of wastewater containing animal manure from nearby agricultural land (Pal et al., 2023). The resistance of *R. equi* to glycopeptide antibiotics like vancomycin limits treatment options and complicates infection management, highlighting the necessity for improved agricultural waste management to reduce the risk of zoonotic transmission (Mühlberg et al., 2019).

4. Conclusions

This study provides compelling evidence that Lake Cajititlán, a hypereutrophic subtropical lake affected by anthropogenic pollution, is a significant reservoir for ARGs, posing potential risks to human and

environmental health. The investigation identified ARGs across 22 bacterial genera, with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* displaying the most significant antibiotic resistance profiles. These findings underline the lake's critical state, with resistance to a broad spectrum of antibiotics including macrolides, aminoglycosides, tetracyclines, and carbapenems among others. The widespread presence of multidrug resistance genes further emphasizes the urgent need for comprehensive strategies to mitigate antibiotic resistance spread. This encompasses enhancing wastewater treatment, promoting judicious antibiotic use, and enforcing stringent disposal regulations. Given the lake's proximity to urban and agricultural activities, our study underscores the importance of continuous monitoring and the implementation of integrated management approaches to safeguard both public health and the ecosystem. This research highlights the intricate dynamics of ARGs in subtropical aquatic systems and serves as a crucial step towards understanding and combating the global challenge of antibiotic resistance. Future studies should focus on the mechanisms of resistance gene transfer among microbial communities and the development of targeted interventions to reduce ARG proliferation in similar environments.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Osiris Díaz-Torres: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Eric Oswaldo Valencia-de los Cobos:** Data curation. **Jan-Ulrich Kreft:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Frank J. Loge:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Diego Díaz-Vázquez:** Data curation. **Jürgen Mahlknecht:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Misael Sebastián Gradilla-Hernández:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Carolina Senés-Guerrero:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The datasets used in this study are available online, and information on the specific repository and accession numbers can be found at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/PRJNA851822>.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172216>.

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